

Rare Earth Elements: A review of applications, demand, sources, extraction, separation, and environmental impact

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ABSTRACT

Rare earth elements (REE) are critical materials used in many technologies, from electronics to renewable energy. Unfortunately, REE resources are limited and concentrated in a small number of countries; and the extraction and processing of REEs can have many negative environmental impacts. Furthermore, relying on a limited number of countries for REE production is unsustainable. This work discusses the relevance of REEs in modern technology and proposes possible solutions to these issues, including innovative extraction technologies, diversification of the REE market, and alternative sources for REEs. Additionally, the article calls for further research on the environmental and health impacts of REEs.

Introduction

Rare earth elements (REE) are a group of 17 chemically similar elements with unique magnetic and optical properties critical to many modern technologies, including renewable energy, electric vehicles, and electronics. As demand for these technologies continues to grow, so too does demand for REE. However, known REE sources on earth are limited, and the mining and processing of REE can have negative environmental and health impacts. Additionally, the concentration of production in a limited number of countries creates supply chain risks. To address these challenges, it is important to explore solutions for both the sourcing and extraction of REE and the environmental impacts of their use. This article discusses possible solutions for these issues, including reduction of REE demand by exploring substitutes, recycling REEs from electronic waste and end-of-life products, new sources of REEs such as coal or maritime sources, and new extraction technologies such as SuperLig molecular recognition technology and solvent extraction and stripping techniques. All these could lead to more efficient and cost-effective ways of obtaining REEs from ores and waste products. By considering these solutions, we can work towards a more sustainable future for the REE industry.

Importance of RREs in modern society

The unique physical, chemical, magnetic, luminescent, phosphorescent, radiation emission, and catalytic properties of REEs make them critical to many modern technology devices and systems (Figure 1). They bring numerous technological advantages for many applications, including greater efficiency, improved performance at reduced energy consumption, miniaturization¹, speed, durability, and thermal stability².

These benefits are enabling the development of faster, lighter, smaller, and more efficient instruments, among other technological advancements³.

Figure 1. Rare earth metals and their most common uses.

For example, REEs are used in the production of cell phones, televisions, and LED light bulbs, as well as in wind turbines and computer memory. DVDs, rechargeable batteries, and autocatalytic converters also rely heavily on REEs. These elements are essential for creating super magnets and mobile phones, as well as for developing superconductors and glass additives. REEs are also used in fluorescent materials, phosphate binding agents, and solar panels, making them crucial components of green technologies⁴. In the medical field, REEs are used as magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) agents and in other pharmaceutical, therapeutic, and diagnostic applications⁵. They are also used in agriculture as fertilizers to improve crop growth and production⁶, and as antibacterial and

antifungal agents. The industrial sector is dominated by their use in autocatalytic converters and industrial catalysts, which are vital for reducing emissions and improving air quality.

The uses of REEs have a significant impact on modern society and play a crucial role in advancing technology and improving our lives, so the importance of REEs in technology cannot be overstated, and their continued availability and sustainable use will be crucial for future innovations.

Market and Demand

Before the REE mining boom in China, the US was the dominant player in the global REE market. However, US mining activities came to a halt in 1998 due to the competition from China and environmental issues in the surrounding area of Mountain Pass³. China's emergence as the dominant supplier of REE led to an increased dependence on Chinese supply. However, in recent years, some countries in Africa and Asia Pacific have shown interest in REE exploration^{7,8}. India is one such country that accounts for about 5% of the world's REE reserves and currently exploits its primary resource, monazite. Additionally, India has almost 35% of the world's total beach sand mineral deposits. Other countries with notable production are the US, Australia, Brazil, Malaysia, Russia, Thailand, and Vietnam.

China has restricted its exports since 2010, for reasons unknown. As a result, REE demand has increased manifold. The scarcity of REE has prompted a search for alternative sources, including recycling, exploration for new deposits, and improving mining practices.

The demand for REE, projected to increase 5% annually by 2020⁹, is primarily driven by the rise of emerging green and sustainable technologies, in which REEs are a basic resource for producing permanent magnets. These magnets are made using 25-30% of critical materials, including REE¹⁰, and are key for motors in wind turbines and electric vehicles. Wind power generates 4.1% of electricity worldwide¹¹, and has a positively growing trend, while the sales of electric vehicles increased by 40% in 2020 with respect to the previous year. Their production is expected to grow annually by 44% in China and 29% in Europe until 2027¹². On the other hand, permanent magnet production will only grow around 6% to 9.5% annually between 2020 and 2030¹³, and, even for that, approximately 83 kt of REE are required. Considering that in 2020 the global production of REE was 24 kt and is estimated to reach 50 kt in 2030, there will evidently not be enough REE to satisfy the demand of green energy technologies.

Sources of REEs

The estimated average concentration of REEs in the Earth's crust is around 130 mg/g to 240 mg/g³, which is higher than other commonly exploited elements. However, REE are not commonly found in concentrated deposits like other metals, but rather occur as constituents of accessory minerals¹⁴ which can be widely dispersed and difficult/expensive to extract. The

cost of mining REE varies greatly, but the economic viability depends on mineralogy, leachability and ease of separation. The principal economically viable REE minerals are bastnaesite, monazite, loparite, and ion-adsorption clays.

REE are found in a wide range of minerals, including silicates, carbonates, oxides, and phosphates¹⁵. The principal economically viable REE minerals are bastnaesite, monazite, loparite, and lateritic ion-adsorption clays. These resources are primarily from four geologic environments: carbonatites, alkaline igneous systems, ion-adsorption clay deposits, and monazite-xenotime-bearing placer deposits¹⁶. Current reserves of REE are primarily in China, Brazil, Vietnam, Russia, and India. China alone accounts for approximately 80% of the world's Light Rare Earth Elements (LREE) production, which has caused concerns about supply chain security for other countries that rely heavily on REE imports¹⁷. Other countries such as Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, Tajikistan, Uzbekistan, and Turkmenistan have also identified significant REE-bearing mineral occurrences^{7,8}, and vigorous exploration efforts are going on worldwide to find new deposits, as well as new sources of these critical elements.

Primary REE deposits are formed by magmatic, hydrothermal, and/or metamorphic processes, usually associated with alkaline igneous rocks and carbonatites emplaced into extensional settings. Secondary REE deposits are formed by erosion and weathering and may include placers, laterites, and bauxites. More modern classifications have divided them into (i) Alkaline igneous rocks: formed by the partial melting of deep mantle rocks (pegmatites and carbonatites), (ii) residual deposits: formed from deep weathering of igneous rocks, pegmatites, and iron-oxide copper-gold deposits, (iii) heavy mineral placers, (iv) REE in coal and (v) REE in the sediments of continental shelf and Ocean bottom³.

Alkaline igneous REE deposits, such as Mountain Pass in California, Bayan Obo in China, and Ytterby in Sweden, are the most significant sources of REE, with Bayan Obo sourcing 80% of the world's Light Rare Earth Elements (LREE)¹⁷. Heavy mineral placer deposits, like those found in Malaysia, South Africa, and India, are also significant sources of REE.

The exploration of potential sources of REE has become more critical than ever, as the world's REE reserves are expected to meet our daily needs only for the next 2500 years¹⁸. Development of technologies for REE extraction from various sources will be crucial for sustainable use and to ensure the availability of these critical elements for future generations.

Metallurgy, extraction and production

The extraction of REE typically involves the dissolution of the ore using either acidic or alkaline solutions (most commonly acidic). Once the ore is dissolved, recovery of REE from the resulting pregnant leach solution (PLS) involves separation techniques like solvent extraction, ion exchange, and precipitation³. Solvent extraction is considered the most suitable commercial technology for separating REE due to its ability to handle large volumes of PLS. The separation of REE is

critical to obtain high-purity products, which is essential for their use in various technological applications.

In terms of REE production, the results of a REE dynamics model of 1465 variables¹⁹ show an increase of 114% in energy consumption in 20 years, which is estimated to grow from 2.55 petajoules in 2010 to 5.47 petajoules in 2030. A similar result is shown for water and green house gas (GHG) emissions. In 2010, global consumption of water related to REE production was 0.41 m³ (million cubic tonnes), expected to grow to 0.91 m³ in 2030. Global GHG in CO₂ equivalent generated by REE mining is expected to reach 169.49 kt in 2030, which is a 2.15 times increase from the 70.01 kt emitted in 2010.

Concerning processing of REEs, the results¹⁹ show that energy/water consumption are 22 times higher than in the mining stage. In 2010, the most resource-consuming elements were Ce, Nd, and La. By 2030, their resource consumption is expected to increase significantly, by 1.8, 6.2 and 15.5 times respectively.

Environmental impact

Modern living conditions and technological advancements have increased the intake of toxic elements into the human body leading to health issues. REEs, which are an important component of environmental elements, require deeper study to comprehend their impact on human health.

The dumping of electronic waste (e-waste) releases significant amounts of REEs and other toxic elements into subsoils and groundwater³. These waste disposal areas can pollute the air, soil, and water if adequate protection measures are not taken. Furthermore, large quantities of REE are finding their way into agricultural soils via phosphate-based fertilizers²⁰, leading to bio-accumulation. Some REE minerals contain significant amounts of radioactive elements like uranium and thorium, for example, which contribute to air, water, soil and groundwater contamination³. REE elements are also finding their way into different environmental pathways, particularly related to ground and surface waters, which contribute to environmental pollution and potential human health effects.

Gadolinium (Gd) is a contrasting agent used in MRI imaging. After being excreted from the human body through urine, it passes through waste water treatment plants (WWTPs) into the aquatic system almost unaffected. Furthermore, there is direct evidence of gadolinium deposition in neuronal tissues due to MRI contrast agent use, which can be harmful to patients^{21,22}.

REE mining and production activities (cutting, drilling, blasting, transportation, stockpiling, and processing) can release dust containing REE and other toxic metals and chemicals into the air and surrounding water bodies, impacting local soil, wildlife, and vegetation in addition to humans³. Furthermore, exposure to gamma radiation is also significant in the mining areas²³. It is especially noteworthy that these activities have led to significant environmental and health impacts in countries such as China, US, India, Malaysia, and Brazil³.

Unfortunately, no maximum acceptable limits for REE in drinking water are available from any international health organization, and there is not enough data available about their toxicity to human health. However, one study²⁴ reported maximum permissible concentrations for different REE in drinking water, which were derived using ecotoxicology and environmental chemistry data.

In terms of resources and emissions, another study¹⁹ estimated that every unit percent of increase in green energy production decreases by 0.18% the reserves of rare earth elements and also increases by 0.90% the gas emissions in carbon dioxide equivalent. This means that actual and estimated future developments in green technologies could cause rebound effects.

Possible solutions for sourcing of REEs

Global demand for REE is increasing rapidly, while the supply remains concentrated in a few countries, making it vulnerable to geopolitical risks. Finding alternative sources of REE is crucial to ensure a sustainable supply chain.

One possible solution for REE sourcing is substitution. However, finding a cheaper and cleaner substitution for REE remains a challenge, and no significant breakthroughs have been achieved yet in this direction³. Therefore, other solutions are being explored, such as improving techniques for detecting possible future deposits and determining the concentrations and relative enrichment of REE.

Another solution is using bauxite residue (red mud) from residual deposits, which has been shown to be a potential source of REE²⁵. Similarly, REE concentrations in many coals or coal ashes are equal to or higher than those found in conventional REE ores²⁶. This would offer the potential to reduce our dependence on others for these critical elements and also create new industries in regions where coal has played an important economic role.

Exploring ocean bottom resources is another solution for REE sourcing. Recent studies of marine phosphorite deposits and ocean bottom sediments reveal significant quantities of REE contained within them²⁷. However, the primary challenge associated with the production of REE from these resources is extraction, which needs to be made economically feasible.

The abundance of REE in extraterrestrial sources, such as lunar rocks, are considerable but low compared to terrestrial ores, making them economically inviable at the moment²⁸.

Recycling of e-waste rich in REE is another possible solution³. Recent assessments have indicated that recycling of consumer materials is a promising alternative to conventional production processes. However, the development of new techniques for extraction (separation chemistry is especially crucial for recycling mixtures of REEs), increasing yield and lowering cost, as well as regulations enforcing recycling, are required. Furthermore, recycling alone will not suffice to reduce or close the growing gap between demand and production of REEs²⁹.

A recent study³⁰ developed new organic compounds to provide cheap, simple and effective separations for mixtures of REE based on solubility differences of the REE complexes. The Department of Energy's Critical Materials Institute (CMI) also developed a method of using bacteria to produce acids to dissolve and separate REE from shredded electronics, which is more environmentally friendly³¹.

Possible solutions for extraction of REEs

Physical and chemical similarities of REE make their determination difficult, requiring new and more precise methods for extraction. Additionally, further Research and Development (R&D) investments are needed for these new processing technologies to be commercialized.

One possible solution is the method developed by one study³² which uses solvent extraction and stripping techniques to separate LREE and Heavy REE (HREE) in apatite from PLS acid solution. The current leading process for the recovery of REE from apatite involves leaching with nitric acid followed by precipitation of REE through the addition of ammonia.

Another innovative technology used for selective separation and recovery of individual REE is the SuperLig molecular recognition technology (MRT)³³. This green chemistry method utilizes nanochemistry principles for metal separations at the molecular level. The PLS derived from ore dissolution is treated by the SuperLig MRT Plant to separate all 16 REE from impurity metals, followed by separation of individual REE with SuperLig resins consisting of highly metal-selective ligand attached via a tether to silica gel or another substrate. The MRT process features rapid kinetics of metal-ligand binding and release, simple elution chemistry, non-use of harsh chemicals/reagents/solvents, ability to recover REE present in feed solutions at mg/mL or lower levels, and minimal generation of waste.

New and innovative technologies like the SuperLig MRT and solvent extraction and stripping techniques³² provide possible means for making REE extraction from ores and waste products more efficient, environmentally friendly, and cost-effective. Further R&D investments in these technologies could lead to the commercialization of REE processing technologies and a more sustainable future for the REE industry.

Possible solutions for environmental issues

In order to address the negative environmental impacts of REE mining and processing, new environmental regulations

and controls must be established in the mining and processing areas. In addition, much is still unknown about REE impact on the environment and human health, so more research is needed to fully understand their adverse effects, their natural levels in the environment, and their toxicological effects³⁴.

The use of REE in fertilizers has been reported to have low accumulated concentrations in crops. However, this depends on several factors such as REE content in the substrate³⁵, growing conditions and plant species. More research would be required to study the safety of using REE fertilizers in different situations and with different crops.

Implications of the presence of REE in pharmaceuticals are also unclear at present. Further research is needed to fully understand its impact on the environment and its effects on human health. This could help to develop solutions that minimize their detrimental effects.

Other solutions to consider

As demand for REEs continues to grow, it is becoming increasingly clear that relying on a limited number of countries for production is unsustainable. Diversifying the market by finding new sources of REEs is necessary to meet this growing demand.

Furthermore, finding substitutes for REEs would also be revolutionary, as it could help to drastically reduce the demand for this critical resource. However, finding substitutes for REEs is not an easy task, and will require significant research and development efforts. Nonetheless, with the continued growth in demand for REEs, it is clear that these solutions will need to be explored in order to ensure a sustainable supply of these critical materials.

Conclusions

The demand for REEs continues to grow, making it increasingly important to find sustainable solutions to the issues related to their extraction and use. A combination of solutions is needed, including diversifying the market, developing new extraction/separation technologies, creating new environmental regulations, developing REE substitutes to reduce future demand, and exploring recycling and other possible sources of REEs, such as coal or maritime sources. Extraterrestrial sources may also become a possible source of REE in the future. Implementing these solutions will require collaboration between governments, industry, and researchers, and a commitment to sustainability and responsible management of these critical materials.

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